

ENHANCING ADMINISTRATIVE EFFICIENCY: A STUDY ON UTILIZATION OF ICT IN SCHOOL OFFICES

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Enhancing Administrative Efficiency: A Study on Utilization of ICT in School Offices

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Abstract

This study assessed the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in school offices across Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools during the school year 2023–2024, with the aim of developing an enhanced administrative training plan. Employing a normative survey design, data were collected using a standardized questionnaire adapted from Taguba (2018), focusing on the application of ICT in four key areas of school administration: planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating. The study involved 59 participants, including 15 school administrators, 23 ICT teachers, and 21 administrative assistants from 23 schools in the Sierra Bullones District. The findings revealed that most respondents were aged 37–47 years, with a significant majority (77.97%) being female. Furthermore, 44.07% of respondents held a Master’s degree, indicating a well-educated staff, though only 8.47% had attained doctoral degrees. ICT was consistently utilized in various administrative functions, with mean scores of 3.43 for planning, 3.45 for organizing, 3.35 for leading, and 3.48 for evaluating, reflecting a strong integration of technology in school management tasks. Despite these positive findings, several challenges were identified, including a lack of ICT training (31.40%), technical difficulties (30.58%), and compatibility issues (23.14%). These barriers hindered the full potential of ICT in enhancing administrative efficiency. The study underscores the need for targeted professional development, robust technical support, and strategies to mitigate resistance to change. By addressing these challenges, schools can maximize the benefits of ICT, improving both administrative processes and educational outcomes.

Keywords: *administration and supervision, administrative efficiency, ict, enhance administrative training plan*

Introduction

In an era where digital transformation is pivotal to organizational effectiveness, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has reshaped administrative and supervisory functions, especially in the education sector. ICT adoption has streamlined traditional administrative tasks, enabling better decision-making and efficiency across educational institutions. Bingimlas (2009) notes that ICT has revolutionized data management, communication, and decision-making processes for administrators, while Mohamad Salleh (2014) emphasizes how internet-based systems enhance task efficiency and workflow outcomes. However, despite these advancements, many schools face considerable barriers in adopting ICT effectively, particularly within the context of the Philippine education system, which grapples with infrastructural limitations and a significant digital divide.

This study is motivated by a crucial gap in research concerning the actual readiness and adaptability of school administrators to integrate ICT seamlessly into their workflows amidst these challenges. With the country reportedly facing an educational crisis (Parojenog & Pabalan, 2024), which complicates ICT adoption, there is an urgent need to investigate how administrative efficiency can be enhanced through ICT in environments where resources may be limited. Furthermore, the generational divide among school staff creates a significant barrier to ICT utilization, as older staff members often lack the digital skills of their younger counterparts (Soja & Soja, 2020). Without targeted training and support for older personnel, schools risk falling short of the full potential ICT offers in managing records, communications, and decision-making.

Urgently addressing these barriers is critical. Schools require efficient administrative systems to meet the increasing demands of modern education, and without effective ICT adoption, they risk inefficiencies that undermine overall educational quality and responsiveness. Studies, such as those by Sánchez et al. (2012) and Venkatesh and Sykes (2013), highlight the need for supportive measures like tailored training and peer-assisted learning to bridge the gap in digital skills among staff, especially in environments with constrained resources.

This research seeks to explore the current impact of ICT on administrative practices in schools, with a specific focus on identifying barriers and proposing actionable solutions for improvement. By addressing factors like generational digital skill gaps and infrastructural limitations, this study aims to provide a framework for schools to optimize ICT use, ensuring they operate efficiently and responsively in today’s fast-paced educational landscape. The findings will contribute valuable insights for policymakers and school administrators on how to foster an inclusive, digitally equipped environment that meets the demands of modern school administration effectively and equitably.

Research Questions

This research assessed the impact of ICT utilization school offices of Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools, Sierra Bullones, Bohol of the school year 2023 – 2024 as basis for enhanced administrative training plan. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. relevant trainings attended; and
 - 1.5. no. of years of being an administrator/ administrative staff/ ICT Coordinator?
2. What extent do school administrators and teachers utilize ICT in Administration and Supervision in terms of:
 - 2.1. planning;
 - 2.2. organizing;
 - 2.3. leading; and
 - 2.4. evaluating?
3. What is the impact of ICT Utilization on Administrative Efficiency?
4. What are challenges encountered by the school administrators, administrative staffs, and teachers in the utilization of ICT to their respective schools?
5. Based on findings, what enhanced administrative training plan can be presented?

Methodology

Research Design

To fulfill the objectives of the study, the researcher made use of the normative survey technique with the aid of the standardized research questionnaire adapted from the study of Taguba, 2018. It aims to see how Information and Communication Technology is used in administration and supervision in school setting particularly in the planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating aspects of instructional management.

Furthermore, the instrument seeks to identify some problems encountered by the school administrators in the use of ICT in their respective schools.

Respondents

The respondents in this study include the complete enumeration of school administrators and teachers from the 23 elementary schools within the Sierra Bullones District, located in Sierra Bullones, Bohol. Specifically, the research

focuses on 15 school administrators, 23 ICT teachers, and 21 administrative assistants. These respondents are integral to the study as they are directly involved in the execution of various administrative tasks within the schools. The role of these participants is critical, as they handle essential administrative functions such as report preparation, communication, purchasing, and other key duties. The numbers of respondents are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondents

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>No. of Respondents</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
School Administrators	15	25.42%
ICT Teachers	23	38.98%
Administrative Assistants	21	35.59%
Total	59	100%

Instrument

To facilitate data collection, the researcher used a questionnaire as the primary tool, which was adapted from the study by Taguba (2018). The questionnaire included a section on the demographic profile of the respondents, covering details such as the school administrators' age, educational attainment, and years of service. This was followed by the main section, which contained statements regarding how Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is utilized by school administrators in the planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating of various school administrative functions. A modification in this study was the inclusion of teachers as part of the respondents.

The final section of the questionnaire was designed to identify challenges encountered by school administrators in their use of ICT within their respective schools.

Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to gather data. A request was made for a list of the school administrators and teachers in the elementary schools of the Sierra Bullones District. Upon approval, the questionnaire was distributed to the respondents, which included both school administrators and teachers.

The data was collected based on the responses provided by the respondents. The retrieval of the completed forms was conducted on the agreed-upon date. Following the collection of data, it was subjected to statistical analysis with the assistance of the researcher's

statistician.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistical procedures were employed in this study to analyze the collected data. To determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, highest educational attainment, and years of experience as a principal, the percentage formula was utilized:

$$\text{Percentage \%} = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

where f represents the frequency or number of cases in each category, and N is the total number of respondents.

The scale values used to interpret the level of ICT utilization in institutional management were as follows:

1.00 – 1.74 (Never Utilized). ICT tools are either unavailable or completely disregarded in the school's daily operations. Administrative tasks such as record-keeping, communication, and data management are handled manually, leading to inefficiencies and potential errors. Paper-based systems are heavily relied upon, resulting in slower processes, data inconsistencies, and challenges in accessing or sharing information.

1.75 – 2.49 (Rarely Utilized). ICT tools are available but used infrequently. While staff may have access to computers, software, or the internet, these resources are employed only for specific tasks or under certain circumstances. Although some processes are automated, a considerable portion of the work remains manual, maintaining administrative inefficiencies despite occasional workflow improvements when ICT is utilized.

2.50 – 3.24 (Often Utilized). ICT tools play a significant role in most administrative functions. Computers, databases, communication platforms, and management software are regularly employed, resulting in streamlined processes. Tasks such as reporting, scheduling, and data entry are predominantly automated, allowing for faster and more accurate information handling. While some manual tasks may still occur, overall administrative efficiency is greatly enhanced due to consistent ICT use.

3.25 – 4.00 (Always Utilized). ICT is fully integrated into all aspects of administrative operations. Every process, from record-keeping to communication, is digital and automated, leading to maximum efficiency. The staff is fully trained in and reliant on ICT tools for daily operations, resulting in faster response times, fewer errors, improved data management, and optimized workflow. Technology is seamlessly embedded, ensuring a highly productive and modern office environment.

To test the null hypothesis, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied. Additionally, the Weighted Mean was employed to measure the central tendency, wherein specific values were given greater importance than others. This method was used to assess the average responses to items in the questionnaire.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to the highest ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring the confidentiality of their information, and maintaining their voluntary participation without any form of coercion. Participants experienced no harm during the course of the study, and approval was granted by the ethics committee prior to the research being conducted. The researcher disclosed no conflicts of interest and presented the findings transparently and with full integrity. Additionally, cultural sensitivity was observed and respected throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section systematically presents, analyzes, and interprets the collected data to verify and substantiate the research questions regarding the utilization of ICT in enhancing administrative efficiency at Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools, Sierra Bullones, Bohol, for the school year 2023-2024. The presentation covers various aspects, including the demographic profile of the respondents, focusing on their age, gender, highest educational attainment, relevant training and support received, and years of experience as administrators, administrative staff, or ICT coordinators.

Furthermore, the study explores the extent to which school administrators and teachers utilize ICT in administration and supervision, particularly in the areas of planning, organizing, leading, and evaluating. The research also investigates the perceived impact of ICT utilization on administrative efficiency, along with the challenges faced by school personnel in integrating ICT into their daily administrative practices. Based on the findings, the chapter concludes with the proposal of an enhancement plan aimed at improving administrative efficiency through ICT utilization.

To analyze the data, both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed. Descriptive statistics provided an overview of the respondents' profiles and their performance in ICT-related competencies, utilizing frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations to summarize demographic characteristics and the extent of ICT use in various administrative functions. Inferential statistics were used to explore relationships between demographic factors, the level of ICT knowledge and skills among school personnel, the extent of ICT integration in administrative tasks, and the perceived impact on administrative efficiency.

Utilization of ICT in School Offices

The use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in school offices is crucial for modernizing administrative functions and improving efficiency. ICT streamlines data management, communication, and record-keeping, replacing manual processes with digital tools like computer-based systems, cloud storage, and communication platforms. This shift enhances accuracy, speed, and accessibility, reducing operational delays and supporting better decision-making, leading to a more organized and efficient school environment.

Profile of the Respondents

This section outlines the respondents' profiles, including their age, gender, highest educational attainment, relevant training and seminars, and years of experience as administrators, administrative staff, or ICT coordinators.

Age

Age influences familiarity with technology, openness to new tools, and adaptability to changing administrative practices. Analyzing age helps identify the unique needs of different age groups among school administrators, staff, and teachers. This insight supports developing targeted training to address the challenges and strengths of each demographic, ultimately enhancing administrative practices at Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools.

Table 2. *Age (N = 97)*

<i>Age (years)</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
25 years old below	8	13.56
26 – 36 years old	13	22.03
37 – 47 years old	22	37.29
48 – 58 years old	12	20.34
59 years old and above	4	6.78
Mean	39.45763	
Standard Deviation	11.04742	

Table 2 shows the age distribution of teachers. Most are in the 37–47 age group (37.29%), followed by 26–36 (22.03%), and 48–58 (20.34%). The fewest are 59 years and above (6.78%). Younger teachers (26–36) may bring technological proficiency and fresh perspectives, while those in the 37–47 and 48–58 groups may contribute experience and expertise. Studies suggest younger teachers often use ICT more effectively due to familiarity with technology, though with proper training, older teachers can also efficiently integrate ICT into their work.

Gender

Gender refers to the social and cultural attributes associated with being male or female. Understanding gender differences in ICT usage in school administration can highlight how men and women engage with technology. In this study, the significant gender imbalance, with a majority of female respondents, may shape how ICT is utilized and the specific challenges faced by different genders in administrative roles.

Table 3. *Gender (N=59)*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Male	13	22.03
Female	46	77.97

Table 3 shows a gender imbalance among respondents, with 77.97% female and 22.03% male. This disparity may affect ICT utilization, as female educators may face different challenges in integrating technology into administrative tasks. Previous studies (Todman, 2000; Russell & Bradley, 1997) suggest that females often report higher levels of computer anxiety compared to males. Addressing gender-specific needs in ICT training is essential to ensure all educators, regardless of gender, are proficient and confident in using digital tools for administrative tasks.

Highest Educational Attainment

Educational attainment influences ICT utilization in school administration. Respondents with higher degrees may be better equipped to adopt and implement ICT solutions, while those with lower degrees may require additional training. The majority of respondents hold a Master's degree, suggesting a well-educated staff, which is essential for effective ICT integration.

Table 4. *Highest Educational Attainment (N=59)*

<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Doctor's Degree Graduate	2	3.39
Doctor's Degree Level	3	5.08
Master's Degree Graduate	4	6.78
Master's Degree Level	26	44.07
Bachelor Degree Holder	24	40.68

Table 4 shows the highest educational attainment of respondents. The majority hold a Master's Degree Level (44.07%), followed by Bachelor's Degree holders (40.68%). A small percentage have Doctoral degrees or are pursuing one (8.47% combined). This distribution suggests a well-educated staff, important for effective ICT implementation. However, those with only a Bachelor's degree may require additional training to fully integrate ICT into their work. Targeted professional development will be essential to enhance ICT skills among less qualified staff, maximizing the benefits of ICT in school administration.

Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended

Participation in relevant training and seminars enhances school administrators' and teachers' effectiveness in utilizing ICT. The data shows that most respondents attended formal courses, indicating a strong foundation in structured programs that likely covered essential ICT skills. However, fewer respondents participated in hands-on, experiential training, which could limit practical ICT application in real-world settings.

Table 5. *Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended (N=59)*

<i>Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Formal Course	36	48.00
Online Tutorials	24	32.00
On-the-job Training	13	17.33
Seminar Workshop	1	1.33
ICT Related Seminars	1	1.33

Table 5 shows the relevant trainings and seminars attended by respondents. Most teachers have participated in Formal Courses (48.00%), suggesting a strong foundation in essential ICT skills and administrative competencies. Online Tutorials (32.00%) are another common training method, reflecting the growing reliance on digital platforms. However, fewer respondents have attended On-the-job Training (17.33%), Seminar Workshops (1.33%), or ICT-Related Seminars (1.33%), indicating a potential gap in experiential learning and professional networking. Regular training programs are crucial for enhancing ICT skills and ensuring effective integration in administrative tasks.

Years of being an Administrator/ Administrative Staff/ ICT Coordinator

Experience as an administrator, administrative staff, or ICT coordinator impacts ICT utilization. Respondents with more than 10 years of experience likely have a deeper understanding of administrative processes and may be more adept at integrating ICT. Conversely, those with less experience may require additional support and training to effectively use ICT in their roles.

Table 6. *Years of being an Administrator/ Administrative Staff/ ICT Coordinator (N=59)*

<i>Years of being an administrator/ administrative staff/ ICT Coordinator</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
More than 10 years	18	30.52
Less than 1 year	17	28.81
4 – 6 years	9	15.25
7 – 10 years	9	15.25
1 – 3 years	6	10.17

Table 6 shows the respondents' years of experience as administrators, administrative staff, or ICT coordinators. The majority have either more than 10 years of experience (30.52%) or less than 1 year (28.81%). Experience plays a significant role in ICT utilization, with more experienced staff often better integrating ICT into administrative tasks. Those with less than 1 year of experience may still be developing their ICT skills and may need additional training and support. More experienced staff can offer valuable insights into effective ICT integration strategies, highlighting the importance of mentorship for newer staff.

ICT Utilization In Administration And Supervision

This exudes the ICT utilization in administration and supervision in terms of planning, organizing, leading, evaluating and impact of ICT Utilization on Administrative Efficiency

Planning

Planning is a crucial function in administration and supervision, as it involves setting goals, determining strategies, and allocating resources. ICT can greatly support the planning process by providing access to vast amounts of data, facilitating communication and collaboration, and enabling the use of various planning tools and software.

Table 7 shows that ICT is "Always Utilized" in planning, with a weighted mean of 3.43. This indicates a strong and consistent use of ICT tools by school administrators and teachers for planning activities such as lesson planning, resource allocation, scheduling, and strategic development. The high score reflects a positive attitude towards integrating technology in planning, enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. Research by Blau and Presser (2013) supports the idea that ICT, specifically through school data management systems, enhances data management, communication, and decision-making in school administration, thereby increasing overall school

effectiveness and organizational efficiency.

Table 7. *Planning* (N=59)

<i>Planning</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
In the Planning of school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Structuring the teaching – learning program for faculty development]	3.440678	0.50073	Always Utilized
In the Planning of school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Planning the seminar – workshop trainings with the use of different software applications.]	3.288136	0.696069	Always Utilized
In the Planning of school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Structuring the computer programs for the teachers to upgrade records and instructional materials.]	3.525424	0.567995	Always Utilized
In the Planning of school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Planning of advance teaching modules for teachers through computer application.]	3.440678	0.565417	Always Utilized
In the Planning of school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Enhancing the teaching learning skills of teachers specifically in the use of technology.]	3.474576	0.597579	Always Utilized
Overall	3.433898	0.590345	Always Utilized

Organizing

Organizing involves structuring resources and activities to achieve organizational goals. ICT plays a vital role in organizing by providing tools for data management, communication, and coordination. Sharma et al. (2020) emphasize that ICT tools, such as project management software, document sharing platforms, and virtual meeting tools, play a critical role in enhancing the efficiency of organizing tasks, streamlining workflow, and improving team collaboration within organizations.

Table 8. *Organizing* (N=59)

<i>Organizing</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
In Organizing the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Monitoring teacher's performance reflected on the Result - Based Performance Monitoring Rating.]"	3.440678	0.623427	Always Utilized
In Organizing the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Using networked record – keeping software in monitoring attendance, submission of grades and maintaining teachers and students' permanent record]"	3.372881	0.69228	Always Utilized
In Organizing the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Plotting the monthly school activities for: a. faculty, b. students, c. parents]"	3.338983	0.632733	Always Utilized
In Organizing the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Complying requirements and reports to be submitted to the Division Office.]"	3.644068	0.482905	Always Utilized
In Organizing the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Incorporating activities into School Improvement Plan (SIP) so as to support teachers in complying requirements and other pertinent reports.]"	3.457627	0.596601	Always Utilized
Overall	3.450847	0.614555	Always Utilized

Table 8 shows that ICT is "Always Utilized" in organizing school activities, with an overall weighted mean of 3.45. ICT is consistently used for monitoring teacher performance, managing records, plotting school activities, and complying with requirements for the Division Office. The highest mean (3.64) is seen in using ICT for complying with reports, while the lowest (3.33) is for plotting monthly activities. The moderate standard deviation (0.61) suggests some variability in how respondents use ICT for organizing tasks. Overall, the data reflects strong engagement with ICT in enhancing organizational efficiency.

Table 9. *Leading* (N=59)

<i>Leading</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
In Leading the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Helping teachers improve their teaching skills by providing professional development programs such as trainings and mentorship to enhance computer - aided instructions.]	3.372881	0.640536	Always Utilized
In Leading the school activities and instruction, I used Information and	3.305085	0.725264	Always Utilized

Communication Technology in: [Determining allocation of funds for more school supplies, materials and equipment (such as computers, projector, printer and alike) necessary for the instructional improvement.]"			
In Leading the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Communicating and collaborating with stakeholders, community – partners and businesses to gain more support and assistance in the acquisition of better technological classrooms.]"	3.254237	0.709376	Always Utilized
In Leading the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Playing a leading role in innovation and promotion of the use modern teaching for the advance learning system in school.]"	3.355932	0.609203	Always Utilized
In Leading the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Disseminating relevant information of school updates and upcoming activities to the whole school community.]"	3.474576	0.536783	Always Utilized
Overall	3.352542	0.647695	Always Utilized

Table 9 indicates that ICT is "Always Utilized" in leadership activities, with an overall weighted mean of 3.35. ICT is frequently used to support professional development, allocate funds for instructional improvement, and communicate with stakeholders. The highest mean (3.47) relates to disseminating school updates, while the lowest (3.25) concerns collaborating with stakeholders for technological classroom support. The standard deviation of 0.64 suggests moderate variability in responses. Overall, ICT plays a strong role in leadership, contributing to improved communication, innovation, and instructional development.

Table 10. *Evaluating (N=59)*

<i>Evaluating</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
In Evaluating the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Observing teaching strategies as well as monitoring instructional materials used (if teachers integrate ICT to improve teaching and learning process).]"	3.491525	0.626233	Always Utilized
In Evaluating the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Conducting inventory of facilities and technological equipment (Projector, Laptop, Computers and alike) regularly.]"	3.40678	0.697746	Always Utilized
In Evaluating the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Checking the updates of Learner’s Information System and the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (LIS – EBEIS).]"	3.677966	0.506532	Always Utilized
In Evaluating the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Monitoring feedback to teachers as their usage of Learning Resource Management and Development System(LRMDS). Learning Resource Management and Development System(LRMDS).]"	3.423729	0.648696	Always Utilized
In Evaluating the school activities and instruction, I used Information and Communication Technology in: [Providing an up – to – date and comprehensive report database on teacher performance.]"	3.40678	0.672582	Always Utilized
Overall	3.481356	0.637937	Always Utilized

Table 10 shows that ICT is "Always Utilized" in evaluating school activities and instruction, with an overall weighted mean of 3.48. ICT is most frequently used for checking updates on the Learner's Information System (LIS-EBEIS) with the highest mean (3.68), while the lowest mean (3.41) is for conducting inventory of technological equipment. The standard deviation of 0.64 suggests moderate variability in ICT usage for evaluation tasks. Overall, the data indicates strong engagement with ICT in monitoring teaching strategies, tracking resources, and providing comprehensive performance reports, enhancing evaluation processes in school administration.

Table 11. *Impact of ICT Utilization on Administrative Efficiency (N=59)*

	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Description</i>
Impact of ICT Utilization on Administrative Efficiency	3.644068	0.482905	Significantly increased efficiency

Legend: 3.50–4.00, Strongly Agree, Very Beneficial; 2.50–3.49, Agree, Beneficial; 1.50–2.49, Disagree, Less Beneficial; 1.00–1.49, Strongly Disagree, Not Beneficial.

Table 11 shows that the impact of ICT utilization on administrative efficiency is rated with a weighted mean of 3.64, indicating a "Significantly Increased Efficiency." The standard deviation of 0.48 suggests relatively low variability in responses, meaning most respondents agree that ICT has greatly improved administrative processes. ICT integration has clearly had a substantial positive effect, enhancing the speed, accuracy, and overall efficiency of administrative functions in school offices.

Table 12 outlines the challenges encountered in utilizing ICT, with the most significant being lack of training (31.40%) and technical difficulties (30.58%). These issues hinder effective ICT use, as staff may feel unprepared or face disruptions due to software glitches and hardware malfunctions. Compatibility issues (23.14%) further complicate ICT integration when systems do not align smoothly. Resistance to change (14.05%) reflects reluctance to adopt new technologies, slowing implementation. The least reported issue is the lack of facilities and equipment (0.83%), though this still highlights potential gaps in infrastructure that could limit effective ICT usage

in schools. Addressing these challenges requires targeted training, technical support, and infrastructure improvements.

Table 12. *Challenges encountered by the school administrators, administrative staffs, and teachers in the utilization of ICT (N=59)*

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
Technical difficulties	37	30.58
Compatibility issues	28	23.14
Lack of training	38	31.40
Resistance to change	17	14.05
Lack of facilities and equipment	1	0.83

The analysis of the study's findings reveals several key insights into the integration of ICT in school administration and supervision. Most teachers are within the 37–47 age range, indicating a mature workforce with substantial professional experience. A significant gender imbalance is observed, with 77.97% of respondents being female, which may influence the dynamics of ICT integration in school offices. In terms of educational attainment, the majority of respondents hold a Master's Degree (44.07%), reflecting a well-educated staff, though the limited representation of Doctor's Degree holders (8.47%) may affect the depth of ICT expertise in the schools. Additionally, 48% of respondents have attended formal ICT-related courses, indicating a strong foundation in structured training, while the workforce is split between those with less than 1 year (28.81%) and more than 10 years (30.52%) of administrative experience, showcasing varying levels of expertise.

In terms of ICT utilization, it is "Always Utilized" in planning (mean of 3.43), demonstrating consistent use for strategic and operational tasks. ICT is also heavily used in organizing school activities (mean of 3.45), contributing to improved efficiency in administrative tasks. School leaders actively engage with ICT in their leadership roles, with a mean score of 3.35, showing proactive use in guiding and managing school operations. ICT plays an important role in evaluation processes, with a weighted mean of 3.48, enhancing decision-making accuracy. Overall, the impact of ICT on administrative efficiency is significant, with a weighted mean of 3.64, reflecting its role in streamlining operations and improving productivity.

However, several challenges hinder full ICT integration. The most significant barrier is a lack of training (31.40%), highlighting the need for comprehensive professional development. Technical difficulties (30.58%), such as connectivity issues and software glitches, continue to impede smooth operations. Compatibility issues (23.14%) also create inefficiencies and reluctance to adopt new systems. Additionally, resistance to change (14.05%) slows ICT adoption, as some staff members prefer traditional methods. Finally, while only 0.83% reported a lack of facilities and equipment, this minor concern still points to potential infrastructure gaps that could hinder effective ICT utilization.

Conclusions

This study offers valuable insights into the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the school offices of Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools. The findings reveal a diverse demographic profile among the respondents, with the majority being mid-career educators aged 37 to 47 years. The high level of educational attainment, particularly the significant number of Master's degree holders, suggests that the staff is well-equipped to integrate ICT into their administrative practices. The study highlights the positive impact of ICT utilization on various aspects of administrative efficiency, including improved communication, enhanced data management, and streamlined processes.

However, several challenges hinder effective ICT integration, such as lack of training, technical difficulties, compatibility issues, and resistance to change. These challenges underscore the need for targeted support and resources, including comprehensive training programs, dedicated technical support, and strategies to address resistance to change. By overcoming these obstacles, schools can maximize the potential of ICT to enhance administrative efficiency and effectiveness.

The study also acknowledges certain limitations, such as its focus on a specific geographic region, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other educational contexts. Future research should aim to explore ICT utilization in school offices more broadly, considering factors like school size, socioeconomic status, and cultural context.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the significant role of ICT in school administration and the challenges associated with its implementation. By addressing these challenges and providing the necessary support and resources, schools can unlock the transformative potential of technology to improve administrative efficiency and enhance educational outcomes for students.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to address the challenges and enhance the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the school offices of Sierra Bullones Elementary Schools:

Develop Targeted Professional Development Programs.

Implement comprehensive training sessions focused on ICT skills to ensure that all administrators and staff are proficient in using technology effectively. Tailor the programs to meet the specific needs and skill levels of participants, ensuring they have the knowledge and confidence to utilize ICT in daily tasks.

Establish a Dedicated Technical Support Team.

Create a team of skilled technicians to provide ongoing support and maintenance for ICT equipment. This team should be readily available to assist with troubleshooting, software updates, and hardware repairs, minimizing disruptions to administrative functions.

Invest in Updated Hardware and Software.

Ensure compatibility and improve the overall technology environment in school offices by investing in updated hardware and software. Schedule regular maintenance and upgrades to keep systems running efficiently and leverage the latest technological advancements. New technologies should be thoroughly tested for compatibility before implementation.

Address Resistance to Change.

Develop strategies to reduce resistance among administrators and staff by involving them in the decision-making process, highlighting the benefits of ICT integration, and offering ongoing support. Foster a culture of innovation where staff feel empowered to explore new tools and methods to improve their work.

Regularly Assess ICT Impact on Administrative Efficiency.

Establish clear metrics and benchmarks to measure the success of ICT integration. Regularly assess its impact on administrative efficiency to identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments to the enhancement plan based on these evaluations.

Engage with Stakeholders for Continuous Improvement.

Collaborate with educational technology companies, research institutions, and other stakeholders to stay informed about the latest trends and best practices in ICT integration. Seek partnerships and funding opportunities to support the sustainability of ICT initiatives.

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